

2D MXene Based Electron Transport Layers for Non-Halogenated Solvent

Processed Stable Organic Solar Cells

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ABSTRACT:

Implementation of 2D materials is one of the promising routes for improving the efficiency and stability of organic solar cells (OSCs). Due to its tunable optical and electronic properties, MXenes, a family of 2D transition metal carbides and nitrides, have attracted considerable attention and demonstrated its potential for next-generation solar cells. In this work, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene was added into ZnO precursors and applied as modified composite electron transport layers (ETL) in PM6:N3 based inverted OSCs. The non-halogenated solvent o-xylene was employed as active layer solvent for the development of stable, efficient and eco-friendly OSCs. By optimizing the concentration of $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ in the ZnO ETL, the solar cells exhibited PCEs of 14.1% and 13.7% for 0.5 wt.% and 2 wt.% MXene, respectively, as compared to neat ZnO layer devices with PCE of 14.9%. Interestingly, the MXene based PM6:N3 organic solar cell devices showed superior device stability compared to the

reference cells. It is demonstrated that the MXene introduced in the composite ZnO based ETL mitigates the photocatalytic decomposition of the organic active layer on the ZnO surface, as analyzed via optical spectroscopy and Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (HAXPES), which appear as a main reason for the improved device stability. We thus report on the usage of MXene in green solvent processed OSCs to enhance the lifetime of the solar cells, and thus address an important bottleneck in high performance non-fullerene acceptor solar cells.

KEYWORDS:

Organic Solar Cells, MXene, Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (HAXPES), Non-Fullerene Acceptors, Organic Solar Cell Stability

INTRODUCTION

Organic solar cells (OSCs) is a promising technology for renewable low-cost and green energy production due to compatibility with Roll-to-Roll coating technology, short energy payback times, and low-environmental impact.¹⁻⁶ Owing to their advantages of being light weight, semi-transparent, flexible, color tunable, and importantly being non-toxic, OSCs support the green sustainable energy development.⁷⁻⁹ Recently, outstanding progress in development of novel donor polymers, non-fullerene acceptor molecules, as well as in appropriate device engineering, have raised the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of OSCs to above 19%.¹⁰⁻¹³ However, the lifetime of the devices is still a remaining bottleneck for the technology, along with the environmental impact of toxic solvents for high performance OSCs, which is non compatible with industrial processing.

Among with optimization of the photoactive layer, transport interlayers deposited between the photoactive layer and the electrodes plays a great role for the performance of OSCs. Transport interlayers are typically added between the photoactive layer and electrodes to tailor the work function of the electrodes, and maximize charge carrier collection while suppressing charge recombination at the electrodes.¹⁴⁻¹⁸ If combined with matching electronic levels, such transport interlayers also become fully charge carrier selective. Zinc oxide (ZnO) has been widely used as ETL in inverted OSCs due to its advantages of being highly transparent in the overall visible spectral range, being non-toxic in nature, and provide proper energy levels alignment for charge carrier selective electron extraction. The introduction (or doping) of various different materials, such as perylene bisimides¹⁹, fullerene derivatives²⁰, aluminum²¹, and different two-dimensional (2D) materials²², into ZnO electron transport layers have been reported, yielding e.g. improved conductivity and electron extraction properties, and thus enhancing the overall device performance. A main drawback remains the photocatalytic activity of ZnO, which in particular for several non-fullerene acceptor molecules has shown to lead to photodegradation of the active layer molecules, and thus significantly hampering device lifetime.²³⁻²⁵ In recent years, MXenes, a young class of the 2D transition metal carbides and nitrides consisting of the general formula $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$; where M indicates a transition metal, X indicating C and/or N, and T_x terminal groups such as -OH, -F, =O, or -Cl, have been extensively explored, as MXenes exhibit high electrical conductivity, high transmittance, as well as good chemical stability. Moreover, MXenes exhibit versatile surface chemistry, and the opportunities of tailoring their surface characteristics and work functions have triggered huge attention for the perovskite and OSCs fields.²⁶⁻³⁰

For OSCs, the processing solvent impacts the surface morphology and film formation properties of the photoactive layer in the devices. Halogenated and/or aromatic solvents such as chlorobenzene (CB)^{31,32}, ortho-dichlorobenzene (o-DCB)³³, and chloroform (CF)^{11-13,34-36} have been most widely used solvents for highly efficient solution processed non-fullerene/fullerene OSCs. Despite halogenated solvents show high solubility, and only minor aggregation for many OSCs molecules, they not only negatively affect human health and the environment, but they may also induce undesirable morphological changes caused by residue additives, and sometimes even accelerate the photo-oxidative degradation of the blend active layers.³⁷⁻⁴² Moreover, halogenated solvents are costly, and they remain one of the obstacles for industrial-scale manufacturing of large-scale OSCs. It is essential to replace halogenated solvents with relatively less toxic non-halogenated/green solvents for commercial production of environmentally friendly OSCs. In recent years, several works have focused on innovation of environmentally friendly halogen-free hydrocarbon solvents, such as xylene^{43,44}, toluene⁴⁵, tetrahydrofuran⁴⁶ and anisole⁴⁷, where decent solubility and film formation of the active layer have been demonstrated to lead to high device performance. Using solvents with very low toxicity, such as chlorine-free solvents, non-halogenated and non-aromatic, ketones, esters, and alcohols derivatives, remains important for the further commercialization of high performance OSCs.

Herein, we propose the use of the 2D material MXene, $Ti_3C_2T_x$, as an additive in ZnO precursor solutions, to develop an ETL for inverted OSCs that tackle the instability problems observed and reported at the ZnO/NFA interface. Furthermore, to develop environmentally sustainable devices, we use the green solvent o-xylene as processing solvent in PM6:N3 (poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl-3-fluoro)thiophen-2-yl)-benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene))-alt-(5,5-(1',3'-di-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl)benzo-[1',2'-c:4',5'-c'] dithiophene-4,8-dione))] : 2,10-bis(2-methylene-(3-(1,1-dicyanomethylene)-5,6-difluoroindanone))-12, 13-bis(3-ethylheptyl)-3, 9-diundecyl-dithieno-[2'', 3'':4', 5'] thieno[2', 3':4, 5] pyrrolo[3, 2-e:2',3'-g] [2, 1, 3] benzothiadiazole) based OSCs. We demonstrate that PM6:N3 o-xylene processed solar cells reach PCE levels of 14.9%, using pristine ZnO ETL. In contrast, with the introduction of MXene in the ZnO ETL, the device shows a nearby PCE of 14.1% and 13.7% for 0.5% and 2% added MXene, respectively. Even though the photovoltaic parameters are not improved, we show that the solar cells with the MXene ETL exhibits superior device stability in comparison to the reference cells. The results demonstrate that using MXene as ETL material in green solvent processed OSCs has a great potential for development of sustainable, high performance organic solar cells with prolonged lifetimes, and MXene is thus a promising candidate for the future large-scale commercial application of OSCs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The structures of the electron donor and acceptor molecules, as well as the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene, is depicted in Figure 1, along with the device configuration and energy level diagram for the layers employed in this study. The work function of pristine ZnO and with $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXenes ETLs were determined by using scanning Kelvin probe system Kelvin probe system (KP Technology), and calculated by determining it of a tip calibrated against the surface of a standard gold sample (Figure S1). Initially, the concentration of photoactive material was optimized in the non-halogenated solvent, o-xylene, using CN as a processing additive, to reach the best device performance, see Table S1 and Figure S2. The neat ZnO films and composite films with MXene were prepared by spin-coating on top of the ITO substrate, followed by spin-coating of the active layer in the same glovebox condition. The current density-voltage (J - V) characteristics were measured under AM 1.5G irradiation (100 mW cm^{-2}), and the corresponding photovoltaic parameters determined, as shown in Figure 2a and Table 1, respectively. The cells with neat ZnO as ETL exhibited a maximum PCE of 14.9%, with $V_{\text{OC}} = 0.83 \text{ V}$, $J_{\text{SC}} = 25.4 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, and $\text{FF} = 70.4 \%$. The solar cells with 0.5% MXene in the ZnO ETL provided a PCE of 14.1%, with $V_{\text{OC}} = 0.82 \text{ V}$, $J_{\text{SC}} = 24.8 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, and $\text{FF} = 68.7\%$, followed by the addition of 2% MXene in the ZnO ETL, which showed a PCE of 13.7% with $V_{\text{OC}} = 0.81 \text{ V}$, $J_{\text{SC}} = 24.7 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, and $\text{FF} = 67.8\%$. The slightly lower efficiency of the MXene composite layer could be attributed to their slightly rougher surface (Figure 3), which could be due to MXene aggregates. Figure 2b depicts the external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra of OSCs with neat ZnO, as well as MXene composite ZnO layers, showing similar broad EQE responses over the wavelength range from 300 to 900 nm. The integrated J_{SC} values for all the devices are well aligned with the values obtained from the J - V measurements, as summarized in Table 1. To further investigate the device performance after doping with MXene in the ZnO ETL layer, the dark J - V characteristics of the OSCs were plotted, as shown in Figure 2c. The devices with composite MXene ETL layers exhibited slightly higher series resistance with values of $2.75 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for neat devices, and $3.13 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ and $3.40 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for the 0.5 and 2% MXene ZnO ETL devices, respectively, which supports the slightly higher FF and J_{SC} in the neat devices. To explore the charge collection and exciton dissociation efficiency in of the OSCs, the correlation of photocurrent (J_{ph}) against effective voltage (V_{eff}) of the OSCs is depicted as in Figure 2d. J_{ph} is equal to $J_{\text{L}} - J_{\text{D}}$, where J_{L} and J_{D} are the current density under illumination and in the dark, respectively. V_{eff} is defined as $V_{\text{o}} - V$, where V_{o} is the voltage at which J_{ph} is 0, and V is the applied voltage.^{48,49} J_{ph} increases linearly at low V_{eff} range, and saturates at higher V_{eff} . Assuming that all of

the photogenerated excitons are dissociated and contribute to the current in the saturated regime, due to the sufficiently high electric field, the equation $J_{\text{sat}} = q G_{\text{max}} L$, where q is the electronic charge and L is the thickness of photoactive layer, determines the value of the exciton generation rate (G_{max}).⁵⁰ The exciton dissociation efficiency (η_{diss}) was calculated by the ratio of $J_{\text{ph}}/J_{\text{sat}}$, reaching η_{diss} values of 96.6%, 95.8%, and 95.7% for ZnO, ZnO:0.5% MXene and ZnO:2% MXene based devices, respectively. This indicates a slight reduction in exciton dissociation efficiency for the MXene ETL based devices. We point again at a non-ideal coverage of the MXene layer, in nature not being a single layer across the device. Tapping mode atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements were performed for the ETL of neat ZnO, and with MXene addition, and the AFM 2D and 3D topographies of the respective films as shown in Figure 3. For neat ZnO films, relatively smooth surfaces with root-mean-square (RMS) roughness of 3.56 nm are seen. For the MXene based ETL, the films possess higher RMS values of 5.09 nm and 6.05 nm, with 0.5% and 2% MXene, respectively. This could confirm the non-ideal coverage and from that potential voids and slightly enhanced trap-induced recombination. That could explain the slightly reduced FF and J_{SC} values for the MXene ETL devices, although the difference is minor in the initial device performances. To understand the charge carrier recombination of both fresh and degraded (after 16 h) devices, we carried out transient photovoltage (TPV) measurements. Figure 4a and b shows the TPV signal of the fresh and degraded devices, while Figure 4c shows the calculated values of charge carrier lifetimes τ (s) for those devices. The avg. lifetime values τ_{avg} (s) for the fresh devices are 2.48×10^{-3} s and 5.01×10^{-4} s for the neat ZnO and ZnO:2% MXene-based devices, respectively. Generally longer carrier lifetimes indicate less recombination of photo-induced charge carriers in the devices, so this shows that charge recombination is higher for the MXene ZnO based devices. This aligns well with the lower FF values for these cells. For the degraded devices, the charge carrier lifetimes obtained are 1.07×10^{-3} s and 4.39×10^{-4} s for the neat ZnO and ZnO:2% MXene-based devices, respectively. Hence, there is a drop in charge carrier lifetime following degradation for the reference devices, which contrast the MXene ZnO devices where the drop is negligible. This shows that charge recombination does not change for the degraded MXene ZnO based solar cells, which remain interesting from a stability point-of-view.

Using deionized water and diiodomethane solvents, the water contact angles on the surfaces of the ZnO layer, and the composite ETL MXene layer, were determined. The water contact angle of the neat ZnO surface was 31.4° , and for the composite MXene ETL it increased to 53.2° and 58.8° , for 0.5% and 2% MXene, respectively (Figure 5a). The composite MXene layers with the relatively larger water contact angles could potentially support enhanced blocking of moisture into the

photoactive layer. To determine the surface energy, γ_s , values, contact angle measurements with diiodomethane was conducted, as illustrated in Figure 5b. The values of γ_s was calculated by using the Owens and Wedt geometric mean equations.^{51, 52} The γ_s values for the neat ZnO layer was determined to be 66.6 mJ m^{-2} , and for the MXene ETL it was 54.6 and 50.9 mJ m^{-2} , for 0.5% and 2%, respectively (tabulated in Table S2). The ZnO surface treated with MXene has slightly increased dispersion component of its surface energy, which could result in stronger molecular attraction and improved adhesion to the active layer^{53,54}, although more investigations would be needed to conclude on this.

To analyze the charge-transport properties, electron mobility values were measured by the method of space charge-limited current (SCLC) on the devices with an electron-only configuration of ITO/ETL/PM6:N3/PDINO/Ag. The J - V characteristics under dark of electron-only devices were measured, and the results were fitted as shown in Figure 6a. The values of electron mobility were calculated according to the Mott–Gurney equation law as the equation, $J = (9/8) \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 \mu (V^2 / L^3)$, where ϵ_r is the dielectric constant, ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, L is the thickness, and μ is the electron mobility.⁵⁵ The electron mobility of pristine ZnO based device was calculated to be $3.80 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, while inclusion of the small amount of MXene of 0.5% and 2% in ZnO, the electron mobility exhibited a relatively lower value of $3.56 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $3.26 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (as tabulated Table S3), respectively. The mobility directly governs the rate of charge-carriers encounters and how fast they are extracted, and the close-by values show decent charge transport capability for the green solvent processed MXene ETL based OSCs.

To analyze potential photocatalytic degradation of the active layer molecules on the MXene based ZnO ETL, compared to neat ZnO based ETL, continuous illumination of 1 sun AM1.5G light on ITO/ZnO/PM6:N3 and ITO/ZnO:2%MXene/PM6:N3 films (illumination through the glass side) was conducted, while the absorption spectra were measured, as shown in Figure 6b and 6c. Compared with the pristine ZnO/PM6:N3 films, ZnO:2%MXene/PM6:N3 films exhibited slower reduction of the main absorption peaks under continuous 1 Sun AM1.5G illumination. The stabilization occurs for both absorption peaks in the blend, where a stronger decrease in the region of 700-850 nm compared to 400-650 nm is seen for the reference films, which is compatible with a stronger absorption change for the NFA component as it has been previously reported.^{23,56,57} This demonstrates that the NFA component in the blend undergoes most degradation on the ZnO surface (in comparison to the donor), and that the MXene treated ZnO can mitigate that. The transmission spectra of glass/ZnO and glass/ZnO:MXenes is shown in Figure S3. The almost similar transmittance spectra in presence of

the small amount of MXene demonstrates that it is not a UV blocking effect that leads to the slower reduction of the active layer absorption spectra in the MXene based ETL.

To investigate this further, Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (HAXPES) measurements were carried out on the High Kinetic Energy (HIKE) instrument⁵⁸ on the KMC-1 beamline⁵⁹, measurement details are presented in the supporting information. The presence of MXene in the ZnO film was confirmed with the Ti K-edge XAS spectra seen in Figure 7a. The main features of the spectra are similar to previously published spectra of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ with a pre-edge region around 4970 eV and two main intensities at 4975 and 5000 eV respectively.⁶⁰ Looking at the Zn $2p_{3/2}$ spectrum in Figure 7b, the addition of MXene results in a shift to higher binding energy (0.06 eV) suggesting that the MXene results in a slight oxidation of the ZnO. Similar shift has previously been observed for MXene/ZnO nanorods.⁶¹ This shift is not seen in the valence band edge, as can be seen in Figure S4. At the same time, a reduction in the signal arising from oxygen vacancies at the O 1s shoulder, observed at higher binding energies than the main contribution from lattice oxygen, are seen from the measurements in Figure 7c. These vacancies are contributing to the photocatalytic activity of the ZnO surface, as it has been demonstrated before for ITIC molecules on ZnO.²³ The reduction of the O 1s shoulder for the ZnO:MXene samples, compared to the ZnO reference samples, can explain both the limited change in charge recombination for the ZnO:MXenes devices upon degradation, and importantly, the strongly reduced drop in absorption upon light soaking for ITIC molecules deposited on the ZnO:MXenes surface, compared to reference ZnO.

To study the stability of the solar cells, continuous 1 sun AM1.5G light illumination was conducted following the ISOS-L-1 degradation protocol, while the J - V characteristics were tracked. We conducted the device aging without encapsulation in ambient room conditions (temperature 25 °C, and 25-45% RH) at open-circuit conditions. Figure 8a depicts that the evolution of the PCE for the cells with neat ZnO, which degrade rapidly for these non-encapsulated cells, and drops to 42% of initial values after 16 hours of 1 sun light exposure. When introducing the 0.5 % MXene in ZnO, an improved stability was observed showing a PCE maintaining 45% of the initial PCE after 16 hours. For the 2% MXene ZnO ETL, the cells maintained 65% of the initial PCE after 16 hours, showing the strongest improvement in stability. For further assessment of the stability parameters, the respective lifetime curves were fitted by using biexponential decay function as depicted in Table 2. The improved stability of devices with 2 wt.% MXene in the ZnO layer results in both a strong slowing down of their burn-in period, and a decrease of the burn-in magnitude, resulting in a strong increase in the overall accumulated power generated over their lifetime ($APG_{lifetime}$), which is almost

three times more than for the reference devices. The other fitting parameters are included in Table S4. We note that for both 0.5% and 2% MXene based devices, the burn-in degradation is significantly reduced. Figure 8b illustrates the aging stability of the devices, in which the PCE is about 45% of initial PCE for neat ZnO, 54% and 70% of initial PCE for 0.5% and 2% MXene in ZnO as ETL, respectively, after 18 days (432 hrs.). The photovoltaic parameters, including V_{OC} , J_{SC} , and FF of both continuous illumination and storage aging devices are as displayed in Figure S5 and S6, respectively. The decrement in the V_{OC} value is found relatively small. This contrasts with the FF and J_{SC} values, which are found to be the main part of the faster PCE reduction for the neat ZnO ETL. The relatively higher water contact angle of MXene could alleviate the infiltration of moisture from the air into the photoactive layer, however, the significant changes in absorption spectra upon light illumination for non-encapsulated active layers points at additional stabilization mechanisms being present. As the MXene does not provide any UV blocking effect, we point at the reduction of the photocatalytic degradation of active layer molecules in the presence of MXene.²³ Such photocatalytic degradation from ZnO arise from defects states, i.e. oxygen vacancies, at the surface of the ZnO. We propose that such effects are passivated by the inclusion of the 2D MXene layer due to the interaction of surface terminations of MXenes with defects in ZnO. The passivation of those oxygen deficient defects are indeed confirmed from the Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (HAXPES) measurements, showing a clear drop in the respective O 1s shoulder upon inclusion of MXene in the ZnO ETL. The slightly lower initial performance of the devices points at non-ideal coverage of the 2D MXene layer across the device, which is supported by the increased roughness. This would likely mean that a more perfect coverage could not only alleviate the minor differences seen in initial device performance, but also improve the observed stabilization effect further. Overall, the exploration of MXenes as ETL in OSCs prolongs the lifetime of the OSCs devices, and demonstrate great potential to develop stable and efficient OSCs with eco-friendly sustainable green alternatives.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, 2D $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene, was introduced in ZnO electron transport layers in PM6:N3 organic solar cells, which was processed with the non-halogenated solvent, o-xylene for the development and study of stable and efficient eco-friendly organic solar cells. Although introducing MXene in ZnO as ETL resulted in slightly reduced PCE of 14.1% and 13.7% for 0.5% and 2% MXene, respectively, as compared to neat ZnO layer cells with PCE of 14.9%, the MXene based organic solar cells showed superior lifetime compared to the neat ZnO based organic solar cells.

Based on the results from optical spectroscopy, transient electrical measurements and Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (HAXPES) measurements, we point at a passivation of the photocatalytic degradation from the ZnO to be a main origin of the observed stabilization, and hypothesize that a more perfect coverage of the 2D MXene layer across the full devices will improve device performance, and the stabilization effect for the MXene based organic solar cells further. Thus, inclusion of 2D MXene ETL in green solvent processed photoactive layer organic solar cells resulted in robust ETL-organic interfaces with proper electron extraction and transport properties for high device performance, and importantly, significantly prolonged OSCs device lifetimes. Given the electronic tunability possibilities for MXene, we see this as a more generic route for stabilization of interfaces to various active layer components in organic photovoltaics.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting information

(The Supporting Information is available free of charge at ...

The Supporting Information contains details of the experimental section, including device fabrication and characterization details, $J-V$ curves of solar cells for varying concentration of the photoactive materials, optical transmittance spectra, normalized photovoltaic parameter evolution for continuous illumination under 1 Sun, and for storage in room temperature at ambient conditions, contact angles and surface energies results, as well as SCLC electron mobility calculations (PDF).

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Figure 1. (a) Molecular structures of acceptor and donor molecules, as well as of the $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene. (b) Device configuration and (c) energy level diagram of the OSCs.

Figure 2. (a) J - V curve, (b) EQE spectra, (c) J - V characteristics in the dark and (d) photocurrent density (J_{ph}) versus effective voltage (V_{eff}) for the OSCs with neat and MXene based ZnO ETL.

Figure 3. AFM height (a) and 3D (b) images of (I) ZnO, (II) ZnO:0.5% MXene, and (III) ZnO:2% MXene films, respectively.

Figure 4. TPV of the OSCs devices with (a) ZnO and (b) ZnO:2% MXene, (c) Charge carrier lifetime of the fresh and degraded devices.

Figure 5. (a) Contact angle images using (a) water and (b) diiodomethane for optimized (I) ZnO, (II) ZnO:0.5% MXene and (III) ZnO:2% MXene films, respectively.

Figure 6. (a) SCLC Electron mobility measurement. Measurement of UV-vis absorption spectra for (b) ITO/ZnO/PM6:N3 and (c) ITO/ZnO:2% MXene/PM6:N3 films with treatment under continuous 1 sun AM1.5G light exposure.

Figure 7. (a) The Ti K-edge XAS spectra for the ZnO: 2% MXene thin film confirming the presence of MXene in the film. (b) The Zn 2p core level spectra for the ZnO and the ZnO:2% MXene showing the binding energy shift from the MXene. (c) The O 1s spectra of the ZnO and the ZnO:2% MXene showing the reduction of the high binding energy shoulder in the ZnO:2% MXene sample.

Figure 8. Device stability of OSCs; (a) PCE evolution under continuous 1 sun AM1.5G light exposure, and (b) storage in room temperature under ambient condition.

Table 1. Photovoltaic performance parameters for OSCs with neat and MXene based ZnO ETL.

ETL	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	Integrated J_{sc}^a (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
ZnO	0.83 (0.83±0.01)	25.4 (25.0±0.4)	24.1	70.4 (70.0±1.5)	14.9 (14.6±0.2)
ZnO:0.5% MXene	0.83 (0.82±0.01)	24.8 (24.6±0.5)	23.8	68.7 (67.9±1.4)	14.1 (13.8±0.2)
ZnO:2% MXene	0.82 (0.82±0.02)	24.7 (24.6±0.4)	23.5	67.8 (66.0±1.2)	13.7 (13.3±0.3)

^a Integrated J_{sc} from EQE spectra. Average values calculated from over ten devices.

Table 2. Comparison of common device lifetime parameters^[a]

ETL	$t_{\text{burn-in}}$ (h)	$PCE_{\text{burn-in}}$ (%)	PCE_{80} (%)	t_{80} (h)	t_{lifetime} (h)	PCE_{initial} (%)	$(PCE_{\text{initial}} - PCE_{\text{burn-in}}) / PCE_{\text{initial}}$ (%)	APG_{lifetime} (Whm ⁻²)
ZnO	1.94	9.05	7.24	6.97	5.02	14.75	61.36	465.76
ZnO:0.5% MXene	4.46	8.27	6.61	13.43	8.79	14.04	58.87	793.89
ZnO:2% MXene	1.36	11.23	8.98	14.10	12.74	13.58	82.66	1268.61

^[a] Shown are the extracted initial power conversion efficiency (PCE_{initial}), the accumulated power generated over the lifetime of the device (APG_{lifetime}), the burn-in time ($t_{\text{burn-in}}$), magnitude of burn-in ($(PCE_{\text{initial}} - PCE_{\text{burn-in}}) / PCE_{\text{initial}}$), the efficiency at the end of the burn-in period ($PCE_{\text{burn-in}}$), time at which PCE is reduced to 80% compared to the burn-in (t_{80}), and the period between burn-in and T80 (*i.e.*, the lifetime of the device, t_{lifetime}).

Table of Content

Non-halogenated organic solar cells employing 2D MXene electron transport layers

